

Engaging with Mathematical Modeling to Understand the Wider World: A Case Study of Primary Teachers' Encounter with Research and Implementing New Learning to the Classroom

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Mathematical modeling is a pedagogical practice that is being introduced in the draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (NCCA, 2022). This research explores teachers' understanding of mathematical modeling as a practice that emphasises complex problem solving to understand the wider world. Five primary teachers engaged with key research articles (Doerr & English 2001; English & Watters 2004; English & Watters, 2005) over three action research cycles and implement the learning in their context. Findings suggest that reflection on pedagogical content knowledge is a lens for teacher change of current practice.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, pedagogical practices, mathematics education

Introduction

With the introduction of the revised draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (NCCA, 2022,) mathematical modeling as a pedagogical practice is described as children forming “models through a process of testing, revising and expressing their interpretation of different mathematical ideas, experiences, problems and situations; typically posed to them as questions or challenges” (p. 29). This research looks at teachers' understanding of mathematical modeling after engaging with research articles and implementing their learning in their classrooms. Perspectives proposed by Doerr and English (2001), English and Watters (2004); English and Watters (2005) that mathematical modeling requires complex models/ artefacts or conceptual tools to solve the real world problems (Dooley, Dunphy, & Shiel, 2014). This research is part of a larger PhD but this paper will focus on one aspect of the study.

Methodology

A qualitative case study approach using action research (McNiff, 2017) was chosen as it would enable complex understanding of mathematical modeling to be captured from five participants in the field. This was a convenient sample. Three cycles of action research (McNiff, 2017) were conducted where participants engaged in an article, reflected on their key learning, implemented this learning with their class and evaluated it. This led to modification or changes they would make to their practice before engaging in another cycle of action research. In the third cycle of action research, the lesson was observed by the researcher. The data collection tools were adopted and underpinned by the Teaching for Robust Understanding (TRU) framework (Schoenfeld, 2016) which focused on; content, cognitive demand, equitable access to content, agency, ownership and identity, and formative assessment. Data collection tools include transcripts of the action research meetings, participant reflective diaries, samples of pupil artefacts, pre and post observation lesson transcripts, and an exit interview transcript that was conducted at the end of the research. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) was conducted to ensure rigour across the dataset.

Findings

Through thematic analysis the overarching theme of pedagogical content knowledge as a lens for teacher change emerged. From this a number of themes arose which highlight teachers' understanding of mathematical modeling after engaging with the research and implementing it in the classroom. These include importance of the task where a context is given and there is no right or wrong answer, thematic approach to complex problem solving, the prior knowledge of the learner, the balance of power when teaching complex problem solving and agency, student voice, mathematisation, understanding the wider world, importance of class discussion, group dynamics and strategies to share learning. The data showed how participants' understanding of mathematical modeling is negotiated and evolves throughout engagement in the action research cycles. Examples of change to practise is evident throughout.

Conclusion

Teachers' understanding of mathematical modeling evolved after engaging with the research and implementing it in the classroom. The findings could contribute to implementation of complex problem solving for teachers wishing to engage in this process in their classroom. This case study demonstrates how engaging in pedagogical practices (mathematical modeling) and reflecting on learning can lead to change in how we teach mathematics.

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